

BIG DATA AN OPPORTUNITY FOR E-COMMERCE

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The digital universe of data is expected to rise 61 percent to 175 zettabytes by 2025, according to an IDC survey. E-commerce forms a significant part of this digital universe, accumulating social media activity of consumers, geolocation services, profiles of web browsers, and abandoned online shopping carts.

While it is nice to collect customer data, analysing the data is what gives a distinct advantage to e-commerce businesses. In the sense of current business dynamics, e-commerce companies using big data analytics will comprehend the buying behaviour of their clients. These businesses, in turn, adapt their marketing specifically to consumer desires, produce fresh goods that meet customer expectations and ensure that staff provide the quality of service requested by customers.

Big data will obviously have an important influence on e-commerce.

This Paper will highlight seven ways big data can foster positive change in any e-commerce business:

- Elevated shopping experience
- More secure online payment
- Increased personalization
- Optimized pricing and increased sales
- Dynamic customer service
- Generate increased sales
- Predict Trends, forecast demand

1.1. Elevated shopping experience

In order to fuel predictive analytics, e-commerce companies have an infinite supply of data that anticipates how consumers will act in the future. The number of clicks per page, the average number of items people add to their shopping carts before checking out and the average amount of time between a visit to the homepage and a purchase are monitored by retail websites. Companies may examine demographic, age, style, scale, and socioeconomic details if clients are signed up for a rewards or subscription programme.

Predictive analytics can help businesses implement new strategies to avoid the abandonment of shopping carts, reduce buying time, and cater to emerging trends. E-commerce businesses often use this knowledge to reliably forecast inventory requirements with shifts in seasonality or the economy.

The largest PC vendor in the world, Lenovo serves customers in more than 160 countries. In order to develop the customer experience and separate the business from the competition, Lenovo had to consider the customer experience.

1.2. More secure online payments

Clients need to know that their payments are safe in order to have a peak shopping experience. Analysis of big data will detect atypical behaviour in spending and alert clients when it occurs. Companies may set up alerts within a limited time frame for various fraudulent activities, such as a series of different transactions on the same credit card or several payment methods originating from the same IP address.

Likewise, on one unified platform, several e-commerce sites now provide many payment methods. "Big data analysis can determine which payment methods work best for which clients, and can measure the effectiveness of new payment options such as "bill me later. To reduce the odds of an abandoned shopping cart, some e-commerce sites have introduced a simple checkout experience. The checkout page offers clients the opportunity to position an item on a wish list, select a choice to "bill me later," or pay with several different credit cards.

1.3. Increased personalization

Big data will cultivate a more personalised shopping experience, in addition to allowing clients to make safe, easy payments. In their purchase decisions, 86 percent of customers state that personalization plays an important role. Millennials are particularly interested in shopping online, and believe that personalised suggestions would be received.

E-commerce businesses will create a 360-degree view of the client using big data analytics. This view enables e-commerce businesses to segment consumers on the basis of their gender, location, and participation in social media.

Companies can create and send emails with personalised discounts with this information, use various marketing techniques for different target markets, and introduce products that speak directly to particular customer groups.

In fact, this tactic is cashed in by many retailers, offering members loyalty points that can be used on future purchases. E-commerce businesses can sometimes choose multiple dates during the year to offer additional loyalty members

1.4. Optimized pricing and increased sales

Customers enjoy good offers beyond reward schemes, safe payments, and smooth shopping experiences. Big data analytics are beginning to be used by e-commerce firms to determine the fairest price for individual consumers to bring in increased revenue from online transactions. Early access to promotions can be provided to buyers with long-standing loyalty to a brand, and customers may pay higher or lower rates depending on where they live and work.

One of Europe's most popular e-commerce companies is Otto, Germany's largest online store for home furnishing goods. Otto has to contend against giants like Amazon to retain the title. In one database, Otto integrated its multiple data silos, making it easier to create 360-degree customer profiles, evaluate competitor data and assess the best performing distribution channels. Big data can now be easily used by Otto to refine pricing, develop more personalised marketing strategies and sharpen their on-site ad bidding strategy.

1.5. Dynamic customer service

Customer loyalty is essential to the retention of customers. Without outstanding customer service, even businesses with the most favourable costs and goods suffer. Business.com reports that attracting new customers costs 5 to 10 times more than selling to a new client. What's more, existing clients invest up to 67% more than new clients.

Companies focused on offering the best customer support are growing their chances of successful referrals and retaining recurring sales. For any e-commerce company, keeping customers happy and pleased should be a priority. But how is customer experience enhanced by Big Data? Big data will expose product delivery issues, levels of customer satisfaction, and even social media brand perception. Big data analytics will actually pinpoint the precise points in time where the understanding or satisfaction of consumers has changed. When businesses have identified areas for improvement, it is easier to make sustainable improvements to customer service.

1.6. Generate increased sales

Big data enables e-retailers to tailor their suggestions and coupons to meet consumer requirements. High traffic benefits from this customised experience of the consumer, yielding greater benefit. Big customer data can also assist e-commerce firms to run accurate marketing campaigns, have suitable coupons, and inform consumers that they still have something in their cart.

Domino's Pizza is an exceptional example of the use of big data to maximise revenue by an e-commerce company. The "AnyWare" ordering software by Domino enables consumers to buy pizza from their smartwatches, TVs, vehicles, and social media. For Domino's pizza sales, making sales so quick and convenient was a vital gain. However it was inconceivable without advanced technology to merge data from disparate sales sources in real time.

Using a broad data network, Domino's data from 85,000 unstructured and structured data sources is easily incorporated. With a single outlook on clients and worldwide activities, Domino's can now c

1.7. Predict trends and forecast demand

Catering to the needs of a consumer is not just a matter of the present state. E-commerce relies on the right inventory being saved for the future. Big data can help businesses prepare for new trends, sluggish or potentially booming periods of the year or organise large-scale event marketing campaigns.

Large databases are collected by e-commerce firms. E-retailers can schedule inventory accordingly, stock up to predict peak times, streamline overall business processes, and forecast demand by analysing data from previous years. For example, during peak buying hours, e-commerce sites may advertise massive markdowns on social media to get rid of excess items.

E-commerce sites can also deliver extremely limited-time discounts to maximise pricing decisions. With big data analytics and machine learning, knowing when to offer discounts, how long discounts should last, and what discounted price to offer is far more detailed and accurate.

2. BIG DATA AN OPPORTUNITY FOR E-COMMERCE:

Big Data provides massive e-commerce possibilities because it allows the online e-commerce shop to closely connect and analyse its digital customers. If the big data is used correctly in e-commerce, "a before and "a after in your online shop experience could make a difference. The E-commerce European Conference held in Madrid in October

2012, reported that big data would be a growth factor that would move \$34,000 million in 2013, using a method for analysing microdata. In 2015 the projections for the study and management of big data will also provide 4.4 million direct jobs. The White House revealed in March 2012 the National Big Data Initiative for Big Data Re-searchable projects worth over \$200 million. A two-year, Big Data Public Private Forum is being sponsored by the European Commission to direct European Commission action for the successful implementation of the big data economy. The next few points are how big data generates e-commerce opportunities:

2.1 Personalization of products for customers

Customized customer support online shopping demand. More and more tailored product prices are also required. Big Data helps marketers to evaluate consumer experiences on all platforms, including social, mobile and online, to decide how they use the goods they have purchased and want to buy. For example, e-commerce should include directives for your complement chain so some consumers can choose features like colour or wired versus wireless with a configurable product. A separate group of consumers could get eco-friendly goods and value added services like gift packaging could be given to another segment. All this can be achieved in real time, using big data to adapt the available goods to the target consumer segments.

E-commerce companies can process this information to segment clients, thereby promoting individual content and promotions by gathering more data from consumers from different points of contact such as loyalty programmes, visitor browsing habits, and past buying activity. This customised content is available through social networking sites, e-mail and online publicity for its customers. Personal purchasing behaviour helps visitors to catch items that are interested in Facebook by clicking on the product that consumers make while visiting an advertisement.

2.2 Dynamic pricing for customer

After the collection and analysis of data generated by big data, a reasonably detailed profile can be defined for each customer. This consumer profile offers insights into the price the customer will take again and convince him to purchase another product from the web. This has proved to be the easiest way to attract customers. The e-commerce web, for instance, will determine whether a discount of 10 or 20% for Rs is the better for each individual customer.

In order to decide the best sales price, an e-commerce company may use dynamic pricing to compete with other e-commerce companies, which includes the inclusion of data from a number of sources, including competitive pricing, regional preference, product sales, and customizations. E-commerce giant like Amazon already has this feature, which has a huge competitive advantage for its company.

3. CONCLUSION:

The e-commerce industry has already been profoundly influenced by Big Data and will undoubtedly continue to do so. 99 companies expect 95 percent of all transactions to be made by 2040 via e-commerce. Big data analytics can be used to update their copy to plan, reinforce their self-service customer support posts, and analyse surveys. Not only should that, e-commerce companies plan for seasonal inflows, emerging patterns, and consumer tastes.

Although big data can be the most effective tool for an e-commerce company, only 0.5 percent of big datasets are used. Traditional on-site systems do not store or process the size and complexity of today's data sets. But what should be done by a promising e-commerce company?

E-commerce companies are turning to cloud-based Big Data analytics to leverage the strength of big data. Cloud-based tools can easily and efficiently store, transform, and analyse information. Talend Data Fabric is a robust application suite that automates integration, making it simple to analyse all information

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